

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

THE PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS DYSFUNCTION OF THE CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND ASTHMA

*Rakhimova D.,
Alyavi A.,
Muminov D.*

*Republican Specialized Scientifically Practical Center of Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation
TashPMI. Tashkent, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract

To study the pathophysiological mechanisms dysfunctions of the cardiorespiratory system in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma. During the decrease in forced expiratory volume in the first second - FEV1 less than 50% of the due and the mean increase in middle pulmonary artery pressure greater than 25 mm Hg, at all patients were revealed signs of diastolic dysfunction of the right ventricle of heart, more pronounced in patients with COPD.

Keywords: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, bronchial asthma, cardiorespiratory system, pulmonary hypertension, right ventricular dilatation, quality of life.

According to the World Health Organization, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and severe asthma with the presence of chronic pulmonary heart (CPH) due to the high prevalence and a high level of mortality are considered to be a medical and social problem. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and severe bronchial asthma (BA) are among the main causes of pulmonary hypertension (PH), and account for more than 50% in the structure of the formation of chronic pulmonary heart disease [1,5,15].

At the age of 35-55, with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) suffers from 7,3 to 10,1%, bronchial asthma (BA) up to 12% of the population in the world. In ten years, the morbidity of bronchial asthma has increased by 35% each year from 100 million to 150 million people diseased with bronchial asthma. In terms of incidence, it is predicted that COPD will rise from the 12th place to the 5th place until 2020 [2,6,7,14].

Since the early days of our country's independence, positive results for the organization of high-quality medical care to population have been achieved, systematic activities have been carried out, and an effective health system model have been implemented. The results of these measures have led to "positive effects in the early diagnosis and prevention of respiratory diseases, resulting in decreased incidence of pneumonia by 49,1% and bronchitis by 32.8% within the last 5 years [3,8,13].

It must be emphasized that at the global level special attention is given to the development of optimal treatment regimens according to the aetiology and degree of development of pulmonary heart. At the same time revealing the pathogenesis of interrelated aspects of the remodelling of the right ventricle with neuro-humoral, vegetative factors of regulation in chronic pulmonary heart is one of the urgent tasks of optimization of differential treatment. An important task is to examine the relationship process of remodelling of the right heart to the parameters of psycho-vegetative status and

heart rate variability as the development of the main criteria for early diagnosis and prognosis of progressive course of chronic pulmonary heart disease, and study the degree of influence of endothelial dysfunction, oxidative disorders, metabolites of nitric oxide and remodelling of the right ventricle heart on the severity of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma [6,10].

Nowadays special attention is paid to assessing the role of neuro-humoral regulation factors and their relationship to the progression of chronic pulmonary heart disease in the patients with COPD and BA, and to develop effective approaches to secondary prevention and treatment of chronic pulmonary heart disease. The above determines the relevance of the dissertation topic [3,12,14].

The aims of the research are definition the nature of remodelling of the right ventricle and neurohumoral, vegetative factors of regulation as well optimization of differentiated treatment strategies in chronic pulmonary heart.

The tasks of the research:

determining the relationship between clinical course, structural-functional state of the right ventricular myocardium and ventilation-perfusion disorders in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma, developing effective approaches to secondary prevention and treatment of CPH.

The object of the research were 57 patients, of these, 34 patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and 22 patients with bronchial asthma.

The average age of patients was $59,7 \pm 3,7$, and the control group (CG) consisted of 30 healthy volunteers with comparable anthropometric characteristics with no signs of cardiorespiratory diseases.

Depending on the nosology, the patients were divided into 2 groups: the first group - patients with COPD, the second - patients with asthma.

Depending on the level of mean pulmonary arterial pressure and presence of hypertrophy and/or dilatation of the RV, each group was divided into 2 subgroups:

1a and 2a of the subgroups - patients with pulmonary hypertension (PH) average pulmonary arterial pressure $PAP_{av} > 25$ mm Hg) with no signs of hypertrophy and/or dilatation of the RV;

1b and 2b subgroups - patients with pulmonary hypertension and hypertrophy and/or dilatation of the RV (RV wall thickness of the front of more than 5 mm, the rear wall thickness of more than 2.5 mm of the RV).

General clinical examination of all the patients included the following: assessment of clinical parameters on the point system; objective physical examination, complete blood count, urine and sputum; test with a 6 minute walk test (6 MWD); testing the quality of life by the modified Seattle questionnaire; evaluation of the respiratory function (ERF) by methods of spirometry, pneumotachography with the registration of the loop flow-volume and computer calculation of indicators for assessing the forced vital capacity (the FVC), forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV_1) and index Tiffno (FEV_1 / FVC) "Medicor" (Hungary). In order to study the reversibility of obstructive disorders of ventilation during the initial study, we used inhalation pharmacological test with β -agonists; study of peripheral blood was performed on the ultrasonic apparatus "Toshiba SSH 60A" (Japan), endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDVD) was assessed by Doppler ultrasound of the brachial artery; blood oxygen saturation (SaO_2) was assessed by pulse oximetry using "OXY" system (Germany); the level of metabolites of nitric oxide (NO) was determined based on an assessment of the total concentrations of stable metabolites (SM_{NO}) of nitrate and nitrite in the reagent G in deproteinized plasma by spectrophotometry method in spectrophotometer "SF-16";

the functional state of the peripheral autonomic nervous system and the adaptive-compensatory capacity of the organism was evaluated according to cardio interval graph (CIG) as described; psycho-emotional status of the patients was determined according to psychological testing using the Spielberger-Khanin scale; echocardiographic indices were evaluated according to Doppler using ultrasound "Shimadzu 500A" and "Toshiba SSH 60A" (Japan), in accordance with the recommendations of the American Society of echocardiograph was also analysed.

A sufficient amount of research has provided the possibility of a representative analysis of material from different perspectives.

Statistical processing of the results of the research was carried out with the use of modern computers like IBM systems using standard software package – "Excel-2012". We used the methods of variative parametric and non-parametric statistics with calculation of the arithmetic mean of the studied index (the M), standard deviation (\square), the standard error of the mean (m).

Study results presents the obtained results in the course of the studies of the relationship between the clinical course, structural and functional condition of the right ventricular infarction and ventilation-perfusion disorders in the patients with COPD and BA (Figure 1). According to ERF, there was observed a decrease in the ventilation-perfusion state of bronchopulmonary system in all the patients with PH. So the indicator FEV_1 was in 1a subgroup - $38,2 \pm 0,5\%$, in 2b - $46,1 \pm 1,6\%$, ($p < 0,005$), SaO_2 respectively, in 1a - $85,1 \pm 5\%$, and in 2b - $89,6 \pm 1,4\%$ ($p < 0,05$), which is typical for the growth of bronchial obstruction. During the echocardiogram, a significant increase was shown in the indicators DT and IVRT, and the ratio E/A was $0,93 \pm 0,04$ ($p < 0,05$ compared to $1,61 \pm 0,02$ CG).

Figure 1. The initial state of the cardiorespiratory system in the patients with COPD and BA, depending on the availability of pulmonary hypertension and hypertrophy/ dilatation of the RV of the heart

Note: the accuracy of the indicators compared with the control group: * - $p < 0,05$

In these patients, compared with the control, there was traced an increase of PAP_{av} to $26,9 \pm 0,5$ mmHg in contrast with $14,1 \pm 2,0$ mmHg of the control group ($p < 0,005$). Shifts of diastolic RV function were also expressed: FAF was + 33.05% in subgroup 1a and +19.14% in subgroup 2b ($p < 0,001$). The ratio E/A in subgroup 1a was increased by 1,73 times, in subgroup 2b by 1,06 times ($p < 0,001$ in contrast with CG). The patients in subgroups 1b and 2b received more acute shifts FEB: in subgroup 1b - FEV_1 $26,8 \pm 0,9\%$, SaO_2

$83,4 \pm 1,2\%$; in subgroup 2b - FEV_1 $39,4 \pm 1,3\%$; SaO_2 $86,0 \pm 1,5\%$ (with certainty $p < 0,001$ for FEV_1 and $p < 0,05$ for SaO_2).

Similarly, an increase of the FAF by 1,56 times was observed in subgroup 1b, and in 2b - 1,47 times ($p < 0,01$), PAP_{av} - 2,6 times and 2,2 times, respectively ($p < 0,05$). The thickness of the anterior wall of the RV in subgroups 1b and 2b exceeded than that of healthy individuals by 6,8% ($p < 0,01$). However, RV diastolic dysfunction and hypertrophy was more common in the

patients with COPD than in BA: 26,1% of the patients with COPD, and 17,7% - with bronchial asthma.

Correlation analysis showed that the increase in obstruction and hypoxemia are closely connected with the development of diastolic RV dysfunction. At the same time, the increase in the intensity of PAPav and the development of hypertrophy/ dilatation of the RV is dependent on reliable nosology. When using the point system (GOLD, 2003) to identify the nature and intensity of complaints, total of clinical signs was calculated. In the patients with COPD of subgroups 1a and 1b, it amounted respectively, $15,25 \pm 0,4$ and $17,69 \pm 0,6$ points; in the patients with bronchial asthma of subgroups 2b and 2b - $12,78 \pm 0,5$ and $14,75 \pm 0,5$ points ($p < 0,01$ significance of differences with the CG).

Correlation analysis between the level PAPav, DFRV condition and total clinical parameters in all the patients showed that regardless of nosology, there is a direct relationship: for PAPav $r = 0,72$; for EDV $r = 0,41$; FAF $r = 0,34$ ($p < 0,05$).

Comparative evaluation of quality of life between patients with COPD and asthma revealed that in the patients with PH, indicators of physical condition (PhC), emotional state (ES), professional competence (PC) and treatment satisfaction (TS) were reduced, respectively, to $2,96 \pm 0,09$; $2,57 \pm 0,05$; $3,09 \pm 0,05$ and $2,59 \pm 0,04$ points ($p < 0,05$ vs. CG). At the same time in the patients with hypertrophy/ dilatation of the RV similar rates were reduced more significantly: PhC at $1,9 \pm 0,08$; ES to $2,87 \pm 0,05$; PC at $3,16 \pm 0,044$ and TS to $2,32 \pm 0,06$ points. The patients experiencing these subgroups feared of physical activity and dissatisfaction with treatment, and found it difficult to perform the usual professional duties. As can be seen from the data, functional status and quality of life of patients significantly deteriorated during the development of hypertrophy/ dilatation of the RV of the heart. The results of correlation analysis showed a strong correlation between the quality of life and cardiac remodelling process of the RV: the RV with EDV ($r = 0,52$), the RV with the ESV ($r = -0,43$), with the FAF ($r = 0,34$) and DT ($r = 0,36$) ($p < 0,05$).

The studies in this area found that: with an increase in mean pulmonary arterial pressure greater than 25 mm Hg, all the patients showed signs of RV diastolic dysfunction of the heart; in the patients with hypertrophy/ dilatation of the RV there is a tendency to a more acute decrease in the quality of life due to the decrease in the physical activity and a sense of satisfaction with the treatment, and in the patients with PH - because of the deteriorating emotional state and reduction of the level of professional competence. At the same time, more evident changes in respiratory function and diastolic dysfunction of RV were identified in the patients of subgroup 1a. These figures are almost comparable with the results of subgroup 2b, which coincide with the data of ATS/ERS indicating that the remodelling of the RV begins earlier and is more severe in the patients with COPD, unlike asthma.

Conclusion:

- during the decrease in forced expiratory volume in the first second - FEV1 less than 50% of the due and the mean increase in middle pulmonary artery pres-

sure greater than 25 mm Hg, at all patients were revealed signs of diastolic dysfunction of the right ventricle of heart, more pronounced in patients with COPD;

- RV remodelling process of the heart and detection rate of diastolic dysfunction of hypertrophic type progress in parallel with the decrease in the ventilation-perfusion state and severity of the disease, which affects the quality of life of the patients.

References

1. Alyavi A.L., Raximova D.A., Sabirdjanova Z.T. Surunkali o'pka obstruktiv kasalligida yurak o'ng qorincha remodellanishining erta tashhishlash usullari / Respublikanskaya nauchno-prakticheskaya konferensiya -Tashkent, 2019. -C.77.
2. Persev A.V. Optimizatsiya lecheno-diagnosticheskogo protsessa u bol'nykh xronicheskoy obstruktivnoy boleznyu legkix // Kurskiy gosudarstvennyy meditsinskiy universitet - 2019. -S. 184-188.
3. ATS/ERS task force: standardization of lung function testing. Edited by V. Brusasco, R. Crapo and G. Viegi // Eur. Respir. J. -2015. -Vol.26. -pp.319-338.
4. Badesch B.D., Champion H.C., Gomez-Sanchez M.A., et al. Diagnosis and assessment of pulmonary arterial hypertension // J. Coll. Cardiol. -2015. -Vol.54. -pp.55-56.
5. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease // WHO Fact Sheet. 2016. - No 315, November. (www.who.int)
6. Chuchalin A.G. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. -M, 2017. 189 p.
7. Haddad F., Vrtovec B., Ashley E.A., et al. The concept of ventricular reserve in heart failure and pulmonary hypertension: an old metric that brings us one step closer in our quest for prediction // Curr. Opin. Cardiol. -2011. -Vol. 26(2). - pp.123-131.
8. <https://www.minzdrav.uz/uz/documentation/detail.php/>
9. Jason T., Rasmussen R., Thenappan H., et al. Is cardiac resynchronization therapy for right ventricular failure in pulmonary arterial hypertension of benefit? // Pulmonary Circulation. -2014. -Vol.4 (4). - pp.552-559
10. Kurbanov R.D. Cardiology. -Tashkent, 2007. - 580 p.
11. McLaughlin VV, Archer SL, Badesch DB, Barst, RJ, Farber HW, Lindner JR, Mathier MA, et al. ACCF/AHA 2019 expert consensus document on pulmonary hypertension: the American College of Chest Physicians; American Thoracic Society, Inc.; and the Pulmonary Hypertension Association // J. Coll. Cardiol. -2019. -Vol.53. - P.1573-1619.
12. Murrey C.J. Alternative projections of mortality and disability by cause 1990-2020 // Global Burden of Disease Study. -2018
13. Sidorenko B.A., Preobrajenski D.V., Belenkov J.N., Batyraliev T.A. Pulmonary arterial hypertension: changing approaches to the treatment // Cardiology. -M., 2011.-No 1. -pp. 100-108.
14. The Global Initiative for Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Revision 2011) // URL: GOLD-Report. -2019, Feb21. - 117 p.
15. Ubaydullaev A.M. Clinical pulmonology // A Practical Guide. -Tashkent, 2015. -498 p.